

Motivational goal model

Thank you for taking the time to contribute to my PhD research! We are currently working on enhancing the motivational goal model by incorporating an additional element to represent resources. This brief survey aims to evaluate the new element, focusing on its intuitiveness and consistency with the other components of the motivational goal model.

Completing the questionnaire will take about 10 minutes, and all the information collected will be used anonymously for research purposes only.

* Viitab kohustuslikule küsimusele

1. Are you familiar with motivational goal models? One example is presented at the picture below. *

Märkige ainult üks ovaal.

Yes

No

2. Which of the following elements are familiar to you? Mark all that apply.

Emotional goal	Emotional goal (neg)	KPI

Märkige kõik sobivad.

- Emotional goal.
 Negative emotional goal.
 Key Performance Indicator (KPI).

3. What do you associate with the shape of the element?

4. This element is designed to represent the resources. Mark all the statements that you feel to be true.

Märkige kõik sobivad.

- The design is consistent with other elements of the goal model.
 The design is appealing.
 The element is easy to remember.

5. Following is the sample of motivational goal model with core elements and supplementary element of resources, and the statements about the model. Mark all the statements that you feel to be true.

Märkige kõik sobivad.

- The design is consistent with other elements of the goal model.
- The model is easy to understand.
- The design is appealing.
- The connecting lines are important to ensure the clarity.
- The connecting lines are unnecessary, it would be enough to place connected elements next to each other.
- The resources element is easy to catch with the eye.

6. This is an example of a motivational goal model with the resources element used in a real life project. Please rate its intuitiveness. *

Märkige ainult üks ovaal.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very intuitive

7. Is there any other information/element that should be added to goal models? If yes, please describe it in a few words.

8. Based on previously presented model, please rate the design of the model. *

1 2 3 4 5

☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆

9. Thank you for your time, we appreciate it a lot!

Feel free to add any comments related to the models or this survey below.

Google pole seda sisu loonud ega heaks kiitnud.

Google Vormid

